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Prevailing Polio Situation in Pakistan and Possible Eradication Strategies against It

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Abstract

Poliomyelitis is a serious health condition that can result in limb deformations, breathing difficulties, paralysis and even death. Although majority of the world's countries have successfully eradicated polio, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Nigeria are still endemic to it. Today, Pakistan is recognized as the exporter of Wild Polio Virus (WPV) due to which World Health Organization (WHO) has imposed a travel ban on Pakistani citizens unless they receive a dose of oral polio vaccine (OPV) 1 to 12 months before international travel. In 2019, Pakistan reported 1125% increase in polio cases. By July 2020, the total number of reported WPV polio cases dropped to 60 whereas 47 cases of cVDPV2 polio were also reported from different provinces. Poor health systems, misconceptions regarding vaccine and socio-political insecurities have been the major challenges in eradicating polio from Pakistan. Low or delayed payments, lack of proper training, and attacks on polio workers have contributed more towards the spread of polio in certain areas of the country. Once eradicated, the world will expectedly generate around US\$14 billion in cumulative cost saving by 2050. With strong commitment and good initiatives, we can expect to eradicate polio from the remaining countries soon.

Keywords: *Poliomyelitis, Pakistan, Wild polio virus, Challenges, Eradication*

1. INTRODUCTION

Poliomyelitis, commonly known as Polio, is an infectious, life-threatening disease that is caused by poliovirus, a serotype of Enterovirus C. This virus can spread from one person to another through fecal route via contaminated food or water and affect the nervous system by attacking spinal cord. Resultantly, the person undergoes paralysis. As the virus proliferates in the body, the nerves cells that stimulate the muscles get damaged. These paralyzed muscles become dead for life and this state is recognized as Acute Flaccid Mellitus (AFM) (Mehndiratta *et al.*, 2014). After the formation of Global Polio Eradication Initiative (GPEI) in 1988, the polio cases throughout the world reduced by 99%. However, three countries, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Nigeria are still under threat (Ghafoor and Sheikh, 2016). Nigeria has not witnessed any wild type polio case in the last three years which means that wild strain of polio exists in regions of Pakistan and Afghanistan only (Polio endgame strategy 2019-2023). As no treatment is known against polio infection till date, the only preventive measure available is timely vaccination of children. The timeline shown in Figure 1 gives a brief insight into the history of global polio eradication.

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Figure 1: History of reported polio cases and effect of Endgame Strategy Plan upon the eradication of polio at global level

Since 2015, no WPV polio case has been reported worldwide except for Nigeria, Afghanistan, and Pakistan. The most recent wild type polio cases reported from Nigeria date back to September 2016 after which no WPV case has been reported (Global Wild Poliovirus 2016-2021). In 2018, 33 WPV1 cases were reported out of which 21 were from Afghanistan whereas 12 cases were reported from Pakistan. In 2019, Afghanistan witnessed a rise of 38% in the total cases compared to its previous year when the number was 29. Pakistan experienced an eleven-fold increase in polio cases with number of reported cases as high as 149 (Chard *et al.*, 2020). Figure 2 depicts a comparison of WPV1 cases reported from endemic countries from 2016 till 2020 whereas Table 1 compares Wild Polio Virus type 1 (WPV1) and circulating Vaccine-Derived Polio Virus (cVDPV) cases reported globally from 2015 to 2020 from endemic and non-endemic countries.

Figure 2: Comparison of WPV1 cases in endemic countries from 2016 to 2020

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Table 1. Comparison of polio cases reported from endemic and non-endemic countries from 2015-20.

Total Cases	2015		2016		2017		2018		2019		2020	
	WPV	cVDPV										
Globally	74	32	37	5	22	96	21	104	174	367	63	135
In endemic areas	74	2	37	2	22	0	21	31	174	40	63	59
In non-endemic areas	0	30	0	3	0	96	0	70	0	327	0	76

1.1. Polio -In Pakistan's perspective

Pakistan launched the “Polio Eradication Initiative” in 1994 (Alexander *et al.*, 2014). As a result of continuous efforts made by all members of the team collectively, Pakistan reported only 28 cases in 2005. This raised hopes that soon Pakistan will be able to completely eradicate polio, however, drone attacks in FATA and rise of militant organization i.e., Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan against the vaccination process made it difficult for the polio workers to provide vaccination in those areas (Kanwal *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, socio-political scenario and geography made the process of polio eradication even harder in the country. In 2014, Pakistan reported 304 cases, however, this number dropped drastically to 54 in 2015 and in 2017 only 8 WPV polio cases were reported. The situation became alarming when this number again rose to 147 in 2019. Till June 2020, the number of WPV polio cases reached 60 which demanded the government to take effective steps towards polio eradication in the country (Pakistan Polio Eradication Programme). Pakistan is divided into seven main sectors: Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Balochistan, Gilgit-Baltistan, Azad Jammu & Kashmir, and Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT). Out of these, three sectors i.e., Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Balochistan are constantly under threat. Table 2 depicts the confirmed WPV1 cases reported from different sectors of Pakistan from 2015 to 2020. Since 2015, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Balochistan have been reporting majority of the polio cases whereas only one case has been reported from Azad Jammu & Kashmir, ICT and Gilgit Baltistan collectively in past six years.

Table 2. Confirmed WPV1 cases reported from different sectors of Pakistan from 2015-20.

Confirmed WPV1 Cases from different sectors of Pakistan						
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Punjab	2	0	1	0	12	14
Sindh	12	8	2	1	30	22
KPK	33	10	1	8	93	22
Baluchistan	7	2	3	3	12	26
Gilgit Baltistan	0	0	1	0	0	0
Azad Jamu Kashmir	0	0	0	0	0	0
ICT	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	54	20	8	12	147	84

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Factors contributing towards high infection rate in these three regions majorly include low socioeconomic status of the families, illiteracy, and inaccessibility to correct knowledge (Ghafoor and Sheikh, 2016). In comparison to WPV cases, the number of reported cVDPV2 has been very low with most of these cases being limited to the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. However, in 2020, a striking increase was observed in cVDPV2 cases across all sectors (Investment case 2019-2023) (Table 3). From 22 cVDPV cases in 2019, the number exponentially increased to 135 cVDPV infection cases in 2020. This greatly affected the polio campaign and highlighted new areas that are to be considered in upcoming eradication campaigns.

Table 3. Confirmed cVDPV2 cases reported from different sectors of Pakistan from 2015-20.

Confirmed cVDPV-2 Cases from different sectors of Pakistan						
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Punjab	0	0	0	0	1	25
Sindh	0	0	0	0	0	45
KPK	2	0	0	0	16	42
Balochistan	0	1	0	0	0	23
Gilgit Baltistan	0	0	0	0	4	0
Azad Jamu Kashmir	0	0	0	0	0	0
ICT	0	0	0	0	1	0
Total	2	1	0	0	22	135

2. CHALLENGES FOR PAKISTAN IN POLIO ERADICATION

All the challenges that are faced by Pakistan in the eradication of polio are an amalgam of social, political and religious complexities. In fact, these issues of security concerns, political instability and religious fundamentalism are shared by all three countries endemic to polio. There are three High Polio Transmission Zones (HPTZ) in Pakistan; Karachi block, which includes Karachi city and is located alongside Arabian Sea, Quetta block, which mainly includes Quetta city along with Killah Abdullah district and a part of Balochistan province, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) and FATA region which is located at the border of Afghanistan (Kanwal *et al.*, 2016) Within these regions, 33 districts are recognized as hotspots or highly endangered regions where providing fruitful vaccination has somehow proved to be difficult (Ghafoor and Sheikh, 2016). Although Pakistan has made substantial efforts towards the eradication of polio, the struggle to eliminate the last 1% of cases is proving to be strenuous. While the wild-type cases of polio are being reported from Afghanistan and Pakistan only, around 15-20 countries are at risk for re-emergence of wild-type polio cases (Investment case 2019-2023). Therefore, eradicating polio from these regions has now become crucial. Among different factors that contribute towards difficulty in eradication of polio, the major ones are discussed below.

2.1 Fallacious perceptions and hesitation towards vaccination

Currently the reported adult literacy rate in Pakistan is approximately 59% (Noreen *et al.*, 2020). In rural regions of the country, the rate is even lower. Low socio-economic status combined with illiteracy and dominance of cultural factors in these areas results in hesitation from parents towards any vaccination. They are often of the view that as the vaccine is provided free of cost from foreign countries and are meant to harm or sterile their children (Kaleem *et al.*, 2021). Few also believe that these vaccines are derived from monkeys or

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pigs hence their intake is prohibited from religious point of view (Haq *et al.*, 2019) From cultural perspective, it has also been reported that as the vaccinators are usually males, and the women (mothers) are not at liberty to allow them to immunize their children without the consent of male members of the family. Similarly, as the cases are mostly reported in far off areas where particular communities reside, they have a perception that this vaccine are specifically meant to target their community (Dubé *et al.*, 2015). Hence, lack of basic awareness is indeed one of the key challenges and is equally hard to tackle.

2.2 Poor healthcare system

Malpractice in the healthcare system is a key challenge to our struggle against polio (Shah *et al.*, 2016). Many families lack access to appropriate medicines and preventive measures and are always at risk of encountering diseases. Malnutrition, poor sanitation, lack of access to clean water resources and poor immunization provide excellent condition to the polio virus to thrive in vulnerable children (Khan *et al.*, 2013). Non-serious behavior and absence of on-duty staff often makes the situation worse. The flawed healthcare system provides an opportunity for corruption as the resources get stolen. The vaccines provided for free administration are supplied to private clinics for monetary benefits, affecting the quality and quantity of available vaccines (Ali and Khoja, 2020). Reportedly, unsatisfactory performance by workers of Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI), deprived around 20% of the children from getting second and third booster doses after receiving first dose of Trivalent Oral Vaccine (TOV) (Shah *et al.*, 2011).

2.2 Lack of responsibility from Government

Although the GPEI Pakistan is fully financed, the country spends less than 2% of their Gross National Product (GNP) on healthcare (Ali and Khoja, 2020). This compromises the transparency and audit of the program, leaving a poorly regulated health sector in hand. The issues such as electricity shortfall, inaccessibility of clean drinking water, food shortage and damage to agricultural crops due to natural disasters have shadowed the importance of polio eradication even in the eye of the government. Therefore, sufficient funds are not allocated towards eradication of controllable diseases and when provided, the management at regional and district level fail to work properly as they know they aren't going to be held accountable (Kabir and Afzal, 2016).

2.4 Insecurity and inaccessibility

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) and FATA regions are most affected by war against terrorism. Since 2004, more than 2000 people have been killed in drone attacks (Javaid and Akhlaq, 2018). This created a panic situation in these areas, resulting in a failed polio campaign for straight three years in FATA. Rumors were spread by the religious fanatics that polio immunization is meant to sterile their children (Kanwal *et al.*, 2016). This, in addition to security concerns, has further complicated our route to polio eradication. The instability in these regions often makes families to migrate from one place to another, making it hard to keep a track of their vaccination (Mushtaq *et al.*, 2015). Also, some of the areas in these regions are geographically isolated and are hard to reach by Government officials.

2.5 False vaccination movements and attacks on polio workers

On May 2nd, 2011, it was found in the city of Abbottabad, Pakistan that CIA was running a false vaccination movement through several NGOs (Kanwal *et al.*, 2016). This revelation badly affected the GPEI and resultantly, different militant groups started to attack polio teams in KPK and FATA region. The drone attacks by the US Government further worsened the situation and the militants ordered to completely ban the vaccination process in the tribal areas as a protest to the attacks. The WHO's special envoy on GPEI Pakistan, Dr. Hussain A. Gezari revealed in an interview that Dr. Afridi was neither supported by Pakistani government nor any of the donor agency to run polio immunization campaign (Rahman, 2013). Blood samples are never

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collected while polio vaccination is administered. Dr. Afridi was arrested by the intelligence agencies and the Government of Pakistan booked him under the charges of treason.

3. POLIO ERADICATION STRATEGIES BY NEAP IN 2020

In 2015, Pakistan military forces gained the territorial control of FATA and other tribal areas and gave access and protection to polio vaccinators in these regions. In the same year, the provincial government of KPK initiated “Alliance for Health” program to fasten the vaccination process and provide protection and all the necessities to the vaccination teams working in the province (Hussain *et al.*, 2016). Resultantly, the cases dropped down by 80% in these areas, however, a rise was observed again in 2019. In 2020, the number of cases reduced by half again. Several strategies have been adopted by Pakistan’s National Emergency Action Plan for Polio Eradication (NEAP). As per strategic plan for 2020, they are not only committed to control all wild poliovirus type 1 (WPV1) but also aim to restrict the spread of vaccine-derived poliovirus type 2 (VDPV2). For this purpose, focused efforts are being done at national level in coordination with international bodies. Rapid detection techniques are being employed so that polio virus could be eliminated from newly infected areas before it spreads. Additionally, the committee is considering implementing high quality supplementary immunization activities (SIAs) and essential immunization (EI) so that the overall health of the community could be strengthened (Rehman *et al.*, 2017). Alongside, NEAP 2020 plans to opt for bold strategic measures to ensure the interruption of polio virus transmission. These measures include:

1. Structural modifications in the schedule of polio campaigns to ensure that adequate time is provided for preparation and conduction of nationwide eradication campaigns. As per their planning, three National Immunization Days (NIDs) and three Sub-national Immunization Days (SNIDs) were conducted.
2. By conducting comprehensive meetings and reviews in 2019, the roles and responsibilities at several structural and operational positions were revised. The process of data collection was also updated so that polio eradication efforts could be conducted at grass root level.
3. Communication for Eradication (C4E) activities were designed to gain trust of common people in vaccination process. Influencers and stakeholders were engaged to dispel misconceptions of common people regarding vaccine safety and efficacy.
4. Area of Work was established in synergy with Expanded Programme on Immunization to improve immunization coverage. These interventions helped in the provision of access to deprived communities.
5. In addition to these, NEAP tried to align Pakistan’s vaccination schedule with that of Afghanistan to interrupt the spread of polio virus within and across the epidemic block (Eradication Strategy, 2020).

4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE AND POSSIBLE WAY OUTS

In addition to NEAP, there are areas that can be potentially targeted for the eradication of polio from Pakistan and other endemic countries.

4.1 Strengthening country’s health infrastructure

An increase in the number of fixed EPI centers can prove to be very beneficial to vaccinate more children. The shortage of vaccinators can be mitigated by training female health workers and military personnel operating in high-risk areas as done in Nigeria (Bigna, 2016). Effective steps must be taken to make sure that a given district is receiving enough vaccine. Administrators should be held accountable for any malpractices. The endemic countries should take India as an example who successfully eradicated polio despite of all challenges. In 2010, they took a chance on bOPV (bivalent oral polio vaccine) immunization strategy under the surveillance of trained staff and by using effective delivery system. Resultantly, they made polio eradication a reality (Garon *et*

al., 2016). Therefore, instead of relying on NIDs only, we need high standard coverage to vaccinate every child in Pakistan.

4.2 Building trust with communities

In 2003, the Nigerian political parties joined hands with religious figures to convince people to end polio immunization boycott. The United Nations also sent a special envoy to Nigeria for negotiation. Similarly in 2005, Saudi Arabia made it compulsory for the Hajj pilgrims to undergo polio vaccination. They also released fatwas (Islamic rulings) to dispel misconceptions related to polio eradication campaigns i.e., vaccinations are meant to sterilize Muslims. In Pakistan, the religious scholars have also released fatwas to convince people for vaccination (Ayaz, 2020). Media is also being engaged to strengthen the campaigns. For this purpose, popular public figures from religious backgrounds and entertainment industries are being involved so that different communities can be targeted effectively. For the future, gaining support from influential people can prove to be very beneficial to raise awareness regarding polio vaccination campaigns. When UNICEF partnered with Imams of different religious schools and madrassas to facilitate immunization, Pakistan's government took some controversial steps by arresting parents who refused to vaccinate their children (Ullah *et al.*, 2016). This approach negatively affected people's opinion. For future, involvement of Pakistan's Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) can create a positive impact on the overall campaign and can help achieve the polio eradication target. In this way, they can reach regions where community healthcare services aren't available.

4.3 Strengthening diplomacy and foreign policies

One of the reasons behind failing polio vaccination campaigns relies in the failure of coordination between health and security agencies. The credibility of GPEI was significantly affected when agencies tried to locate Osama bin Laden using fake vaccination campaign (Tiefengraber, 2013). Additionally, it has been reported that health workers have been used for intelligence purposes. As polio vaccination is provided to Pakistan as foreign aid, these issues jeopardize the overall healthcare goals. In the present era, global health initiatives reflect diplomatic and security interests of both donor and recipient countries. Immunization against infectious diseases and health security is demanded by many European and gulf countries from their residents (Steurs *et al.*, 2018). In Pakistan, GPEI and government are connected, and the military forces play a significant role in aiding the process of immunization in the tribal areas. However, facilitation is required in terms of access to better healthcare in hard-to-reach areas. One major reason of failure of polio eradication campaign in Pakistan lies in the inability of healthcare professionals to understand the religious and social sentiments of people that are affected (Butt *et al.*, 2020). The government officials from federal to local level should address these issues by aligning their primary health goals with that of local communities. For this purpose, they can partner with social welfare organizations that are working and are trusted by people in those areas. On broader level, standard protocols should be established for the evaluation, design, and delivery of these programs under the supervision of foreign policy makers and economists alongside with healthcare professionals (Alonge *et al.*, 2020). In this manner, the campaigns will become acceptable and transparent to people, making goals easier to achieve.

4.4 Vaccinating High Polio Transmission Zones on priority

National Emergency Action Plan (NEAP) for Polio Eradication includes Sub-National Immunization Activities (SIA) on priority in HPTZs across the country. There are 12 districts including Karachi, Quetta and parts of FATA are endemic to polio and are recognized as 'Reservoir Districts' whereas 30 districts, majorly located in southern FATA and KP are categorized as 'High Risk Districts' (Hussain *et al.*, 2016) Additionally, there are 11 districts which are noted as 'Outbreak Districts' in the SIA calendar. The rest of the areas in Pakistan fall under the category of low-risk districts in National Immunization Day (NID) calendar (Eradication Strategy, 2020). Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) are to be vaccinated at Permanent Transit Points (PTPs) in KP and FATA region near the border of Afghanistan. This step is crucial as this point may become the source of infection for

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other parts of the country. All these efforts are planned to be conducted in collaboration with military forces to further reduce the rate of poliomyelitis cases by the end of 2021.

5. CONCLUSION

Although Pakistan is very committed to get rid of polio, there is still a long way to go. Effective strategy is to be implemented at ground level especially in the tribal belt located along the northwestern border. The health policies should be aligned with the foreign policies and should be considered as seriously as matters of national security. The current challenges can be overcome not only by improvisation in health infrastructure but also by collaboration of healthcare professionals with the diplomats, policymakers, and non-profit organizations. Only by amalgamation of strategic approaches, we can make polio eradication from Pakistan a reality.

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